

Virtual Physics Laboratory

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Abstract: Laboratory experiments are an essential part of a physics course. In March 2020 a virtual physics laboratory was designed and implemented due to the Corona pandemic. Documents, photos, videos and simulations of the experiments are made available via the learning management system Moodle. The evaluation of the values determined by the students is carried out with the help of the plugin STACK (System for Teaching and Assessment using a Computer algebra Kernel). This article explains the implementation of the virtual lab and shows an example of a STACK question.

Keywords: physics laboratory, virtual experiments, Moodle, plugin STACK

1 Introduction

As a university of applied sciences, we are committed to providing students with practical training in addition to the lectures in the physics course. Each semester, students from 6 Bachelor programmes participate in 3 to 7 different laboratory experiments.

When it became clear at the end of March 2020 that, due to the Corona pandemic, students could not attend the physics lab in person during the summer term, a completely virtual physics lab was designed and implemented. The point of a laboratory experiment is basically to offer students a "hands on" experience. Therefore, a virtual lab can of course never offer the same learning experience as a lab that students attend in person. However, due to the high number of participants, the virtual implementation was the only possible option in the current situation.

2 Preliminary work

The development of the virtual alternative in a short time frame was only possible because of the preliminary work that had already been done. A few years ago, we started to implement the mandatory safety instruction with the help of a Moodle course [Mo21]. In addition, the documents for preparing the experiments were made available via the learning management system Moodle.

Repeatedly lecturers and laboratory staff complained about the sometimes inadequate preparation of the students. For this reason, Moodle tests were introduced, in which the

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knowledge required for the experiments was checked. Passing these tests was a prerequisite for the permission to participate in the experiment. According to the laboratory staff, the students came to the experiments much better prepared, after the introduction of these tests. The use of randomly selected questions and calculation questions with random numbers ensures that all students have to complete the tests individually.

In the winter term 2019/20, students still had to print out and fill out the laboratory documents (10-15 pages per experiment) and submit them in a folder. The switch to file submission of the protocols via Moodle saves paper and makes it easier to correct and grade the protocols.

3 Sequence of processing in the experiments

The sequence of the necessary steps in the virtual laboratory experiments is shown in the following diagram:

Fig. 1: Sequence of processing in the experiments

After enrolling in the Moodle course, all students only see the experiments relevant to them (1). For each experiment, a document with the basic knowledge is available, which the students have to work through in advance (2). A Moodle test must then be completed in which the required basic knowledge is checked (3). For some experiments, questions had to be answered in writing and uploaded as a file (4). Since last winter term, there are only tests in the preparation and no more file submissions. If the preparation test has been successfully completed, admission to the experiment is obtained (5). Photos and videos of the experiments have been taken by the laboratory staff, which are used to determine the measured values (6). If results are to be calculated, these must be entered in a Moodle test in which the calculations are automatically checked on the basis of the individual values (7). For some experiments, the protocol must be uploaded as a file or additional diagrams must be uploaded (8). If all steps have been accomplished successfully, then the experiment is complete (9).

4 Implementation of the experiments

The experiment instructions were inserted directly into Moodle as a text page. The photos and videos are located in a separate directory and are integrated via a link. The students carry out the experiment by following the experiment description. For example, they have to measure values with a micrometer screw using photos, measure durations using the videos or note values of measuring devices.

The measured values, which the students determine during the experiments, must be recorded in a protocol. For some experiments, the protocol must be submitted as a file in Moodle or additional diagrams must be uploaded. In all experiments where this is possible and makes sense, the evaluation of the measurement results is automated in a Moodle test.

5 Evaluation of the measured values

In the Moodle test, the plugin STACK [UE21] is used to check the measured values and the calculations carried out by the students on the basis of the individual values.

This type of evaluation differs considerably from the standard evaluation in Moodle tests. Usually, a Moodle test contains questions where the expected solution is already determined when the question is created. In our case, the system must first calculate a solution based on the individually determined and entered values of the measurement and then compare this with the solution entered by the students. This particular functionality is made possible by the STACK plugin [MPD21].

Frage **1**
Teilweise richtig
Erreichte Punkte
0,59 von 1,00

Abschätzung des Massenträgheitsmoments einer Hantel

Masse der Hantel: $m = 4.155$ kg

Abstand: $a = 0.12$ m

Scheibenradius: $R = 0.098$ m

Massenträgheitsmoment (grobe Näherung): $I_1 = 0.0598$ kg·m²

Massenträgheitsmoment (verbesserte Näherung): $I_2 = 0.0662$ kg·m²

Die Antwort ist teilweise richtig.

Ihr Messwert für den Radius R liegt außerhalb der erwarteten Toleranz.

Sie haben das Massenträgheitsmoment I_1 richtig berechnet.

Sie haben das Massenträgheitsmoment I_2 nicht richtig berechnet.

Fig. 2: Example from the experiment "Torsion pendulum"

The feedback in the question above is:

The answer is partially correct.

Your measured value for the radius R is not within the expected tolerance.

You have calculated the mass moment of inertia I_1 correctly.

You have not calculated the mass moment of inertia I_2 correctly.

The example above from the experiment "Torsion pendulum" contains only a few input fields, usually there are many more. As a response, the students receive detailed feedback on the values entered.

The averages and tolerances are defined in the question variables. In the first part of the potential response tree, the entered values are being checked. The students first receive feedback on whether they have measured the values correctly, which means whether the measured values are within the expected tolerance.

Question name V03 Torsionspendel - Massenträgheitsmoment, Torsionskonstante

Question tests & deployed versions

Question variables

```
simp: true;
mw_m: 4.155; tol_m: 0.03;
mw_a: 0.12; tol_a: 0.005;
mw_R: 0.0785; tol_R: 0.002;
mw_I1: mw_m*mw_a^2;
mw_I2: 1/4*mw_m*mw_R^2+mw_m*mw_a^2;
```

Fig. 3: Definition of the averages and tolerances

The actual calculations are carried out in the feedback variables.

Question value

Auto-simplify

Feedback variables

```
simp: true;
I1: ans_m*ans_a^2;
I2: 1/4*ans_m*ans_R^2+ans_m*ans_a^2;
```

Fig. 4: Calculation of the correct solutions

In the second part of the potential response tree, the calculated values entered by the students are compared with the values that the system has determined as correct solutions, based on the measured values.

The screenshot displays a Moodle question interface for 'Node 1'. The question type is 'Answer test' with the question text 'NumAbsolute'. The SAns field contains 'ans_1' and the TAns field contains 'I1'. The test options are set to '0.002', 'Quiet', and 'No'. The 'Node 1 when true' section is highlighted in green, showing a score of 0.5 and a feedback message: 'Sie haben das Massenträgheitsmoment I_1 richtig berechnet.' The 'Node 1 when false' section is highlighted in red, showing a score of 0 and a feedback message: 'Sie haben das Massenträgheitsmoment I_1 nicht richtig berechnet.'

Fig. 5: Evaluation of the calculated values

6 Conclusion

At the beginning, the tolerances in the automatic evaluation of the test results were too narrow. It was very difficult to estimate how large the deviations would be in the evaluation based on the photos and videos. The tolerances were therefore adjusted after a short time based on the actual inputs.

The implementation of the automated evaluation considerably reduced the workload for the correction of the protocols. Before the implementation of the automated evaluation, the correctors recalculated the values either with a pocket calculator or by entering them in a spreadsheet application. This very time-consuming process during correction is now eliminated.

Finally, it can be said that the virtual physics laboratory was considered as a good alternative in the special situation by most of the students. Despite the generally difficult situation, the experiments were successfully completed by the majority of the students.

Bibliography

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